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DEVELOPMENT INTERVENTION STRATEGIES FOR EMPOWERMENT OF RURAL POPULATION

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Abstract

The role of Project administrators is to identify the suitable development intervention to instill new skill and knowledge to the participants. This paper aims to study the management of training programme with respect to various activities carried out in training programme with respect to duration of training, Curricula, implementing course and follow up measures. The variable identified are Activities followed in training programme, Duration of training, Review of curricula, Mechanisms for mid course correction, Follow up measures on utilization of training program. Out of various activities, majority provided independent practice to participants. In feedback system, none of them used suggestion box. In case of follow up measures, majority have arranged meeting with banks and financial institutions to support the beneficiaries for exploring the financial assistance for starting own unit.

Key words: Empowerment, Gender equity, Rural Development, Rural population, skill development, Training,

Introduction - Human Resource Development

The goal of human resource development is to provide a trained work force, and to promote the knowledge and skills required by a society to build productive capabilities. According to Peter F. Drucker, "Knowledge is information that changes something or somebody -- either by becoming grounds for actions, or by making an individual (or an institution) capable of different or more effective action". According to Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), the provision of basic education constitutes the best long-term investment, favoring the most disadvantaged groups in particular. Training and skill development are essential for farmers to obtain better benefit from new technology and market opportunities and to react to risk. Basic education affects the productivity of small landholders and subsistence farmers immediately and positively. According to Martin Carnoy (1992), a farmer with four years of elementary education is, on average, 8.7 per cent more productive than a farmer with no education. Moreover, farmers with more education get higher gains in income from the use of new technologies and adjust more rapidly to technological changes⁵. Lavinia Gasperini (2000) pointed out that the provision of more and better basic educational services in rural areas such as primary education, literacy and basic skills training can substantially improve productivity and livelihoods⁶. Lavinia Gasperini (2001) states that the Food and Agricultural Organisation's education group identified the following as priorities areas for systemic action: Expand access to education among rural children, youth and adults (for example, by teaching students to provide food for themselves from school gardens and canteens, utilizing distance education, focusing on education for rural girls and women and life- long education), improve the quality of

education (for example by enriching the curriculum with participatory curriculum planning methods, introducing environmental and nutrition education, basic financial literacy, and HIV/AIDS prevention; reforming technical and vocational education to face the new challenges in agriculture and rural development; improving the quality of both Technical and Vocational Education available to farmers and of higher education).

Empowerment

Rural poor has feelings that they are incapable of doing work on their own and depends on others. John W. Newstrom and Keith Davis (1999), states that this powerlessness contributes to the frustrating experience of low self-efficacy – the conviction among people that they cannot successfully perform their jobs or make meaningful contributions. Robert C Ford and Myron D.Fottler (1995) stated that empowerment helps to remove the conditions that cause powerlessness while enhancing employee feelings of self- efficacy. Empowerment means provision of new skill and knowledge in addition to the existing capacity of the beneficiaries to act independently to control the available resources to satisfy their own requirements. The ultimate aim of empowerment is gender equality by ensuring balanced growth of men and women in society.

Gender equality

Sustainable development recognizes that all development decisions must simultaneously consider aspects of economy, environment, and equity. Gender equality means that women and men enjoy the same status. Further, women and men have equal conditions for realizing their full human rights and potential to contribute to national, political, economic, social and cultural development, and to benefit from the results.

Objectives of the study

Development intervention is major aspect towards redefining activities of organization involved in rural development. The following are the objectives of this study.

To study the management of training programme with respect to various activities carried out in training programme with respect to duration of training, Curricula, implementing course and follow up measures.

The variable identified are Activities followed in training programme, Duration of training, Review of curricula, Mechanisms for mid course correction, Follow up measures on utilization of training program.

Methodology

The survey method is used to collect data by using questionnaire from project administrators of the development programme. Out of 54 institutions conducting development programmes, a sample of 40 project administrators were selected randomly.

Activities followed in training programme

Training programme shall consist of various activities to achieve the object of the programme. The eight programmes were identified in this study and responses about the programmes offered are shown in Table 1.

The table 1 depicts the distribution of various activities mentioned above. It is highlighted that 95% of respondents provided of independent practice by beneficiaries. In case of visit to industry and exhibitions, 50% of respondents were organising the visits and 35% of respondents proposed to conduct it in future. 80% of respondents arranged for on the job training. 40% of respondents included the problems of marketing and 35%of respondents planned this for the future. In case of accounting concepts, 30% of respondents have included in their programme and 35% of them proposed for future. In case of supply of notes and pamphlets, 90% of them were following the practice. Usage of computer is practiced provided by 80% of respondents. It can be observed that provision of independent

practice to beneficiaries, supply of notes and pamphlets and on the job training are the activities were practiced by majority of the respondents.

Table 1- Activities followed in training programme

Training Programs Provide The Following		YES	NO	PROPOSED
Provision of independent practice	No.	38	2	0
	%	95.0	5.0	0
Visit to industry and exhibitions	No.	20	6	14
	%	50.0	15.0	35.0
On the job training	No.	32	4	4
	%	80.0	10.0	10.0
Inclusion of marketing problems	No.	16	10	14
	%	40.0	25.0	35.0
Teaching accounting concept	No.	12	14	14
	%	30.0	35.0	35.0
Provision of notes and pamphlets	No.	36	2	2
	%	90.0	5.0	5.0
Usage of computers	No.	32	2	6
	%	80.0	5.0	15.0
Entrepreneurial training	No.	30	0	10
	%	75.0	0	25.0

Duration of training

The duration of course will influence the participation of rural people. The preference of project administrators will be based on the liking of the beneficiaries for duration of training. Preference for duration course is depicted in Table 2. The table shows that 40% of the Project administrators preferred equally less than 1 month and 3-6 months duration of course. 20% of them have preferred 1-3 months duration. It can be observed that 1 and 6 months duration is generally preferred by the project administrators.

Table 2- Duration of training

DURATION	No.	Percent
LESS THAN 1 MONTH	16	40.0
	8	20.0
3-6 MONTH	16	40.0
Total	40	100.0

Review of curricula

Curriculum review is to be done periodically to update the technology. Respondents were asked to give information on the time in which they plan to review the curriculum of the training and shown in Table 3.

Table 3 - Review of curricula

PERIOD FOR REVIEW OF CURRICULA	No.	Percent
Once in six months	12	30.0
Once in a year	22	55.0
Whenever is required	6	15.0
Total	40	100.0

Table 3 shows that majority of respondents were reviewing the curricula once in a year. Small percentage of respondents was reviewing whenever it is required. 30% of them favoring once in six months review.

Mechanisms for mid course correction

The programme can be controlled by getting feedbacks from the connected persons. Organizers have to follow proper feedback mechanism for identifying any deviation while conducting course. In this study, preference for feedback mechanism for mid course correction was collected from sample of Project Officers and shown in Table 4.

Table 4 shows that 72.2% of respondents preferred the formal feedback form. 22.2% of respondents preferred Group discussion method. 16.7% of respondents preferred Interview method. 11.2% of respondents revealed preference for interview method. None of them have chosen the suggestion box method. It can be noted that formal feedback form is popular method among the Project Officer respondents.

Table 4 - Mechanisms for mid course correction

Mechanisms used for mid course correction-multiple response	No.	%
Suggestion box	0	0
Formal feedback form	26	72.2
Interview method	4	11.1
Group discussion	8	22.2
Voluntary suggestion	6	16.7

Follow up measures on utilization of training program

Follow up measures are essential to encourage the beneficiaries to take necessary steps towards empowerment by utilizing the benefits of training. Seven activities are identified and responses were given in three option such as Yes, No, Planned.

Table 5 displays the percentage distribution of follow up measures on utilization of training benefits. The table shows that 75% of respondents have arranged meeting with banks and financial institutions to support the beneficiaries for exploring the financial assistance for starting own unit. 65% of respondents have arranged Meeting with District Industrial centre (DIC) and other local authorities for preparation of new project proposals. 60% of respondents are visiting beneficiary's work place to assess utility of training and suggest for remedy any deviations. 35% of respondents accepted arrangement of consultation with experts and 45% preferred this as future activities. 60% of respondents arranged group formation and arrange for common facilities. 65% of respondents provided guidelines on latest technology by issuing pamphlets. It can be noted that majority of respondents took follow up steps to encourage the beneficiaries to utilise the programme.

Table 5- Follow up measures on utilization of training program

Follow-up measures on utilization of training program				
		YES	NO	PLANNED
1. Meetings are arranged with banks and financial institutions for support.	No.	30	2	8
	%	75.0	5.0	20.0
2. Meetings are arranged with District Industrial centre, and with local authorities for opportunities.	No.	26	2	12
	%	65.0	5.0	30.0
3. Visiting beneficiaries' work place to assess utility of training.	No.	24	6	10
	%	60.0	15.0	25.0
4. Inviting beneficiaries for review of training.	No.	20	2	18
	%	50.0	5.0	45.0
5. Arrange the experts for consultation.	No.	14	8	18
	%	35.0	20.0	45.0
6. Group formation and arrange for common facilities.	No.	24	2	14
	%	60.0	5.0	35.0
7. Provides guidelines on latest technology.	No.	26	3	11
	%	65.0	7.5	27.5

Findings

The study found the following results:

Out of various activities, 95% of respondents provided of independent practice to beneficiaries. In case of visit to industry and exhibitions, 50% of respondents were organising the visits and 35% of respondents proposed to conduct it in future. 80% of respondents arranged for on the job training. Regarding duration of training, 40% of the Project administrators preferred equally less than 1 month and 3-6 months duration of course. In case of review of curricula, majority of respondents were reviewing the curricula once in a year. Out several feedback systems followed, 72.2% of respondents preferred the formal feedback form. None of them have chosen the suggestion box method. In case of follow up measures, 75% of respondents have arranged meeting with banks and financial institutions to support the beneficiaries for exploring the financial assistance for starting own unit.

Conclusion

It is inferred from the study, the development programmes may be effectively implemented by following certain important factors. Project administrators may concentrate on industrial visits by participants. In feedback system for mid course correction, suggestion box was completely neglected. The participants may freely express their critical opinion in suggestion box. In follow up measures, Project administrators may consider the factors such as visiting beneficiaries' work place to assess utility of training. Inviting beneficiaries for review of training, arrange the experts for consultation.

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